

Studies on the Properties of Large Ions in Solvents of High Dielectric Constants—Part II Electrical Conductance of Some Salts Containing An Ion With a Long Alkyl Chain in NMA, DMF and DMA

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A study of electrical conductance of solutions of some cation and anion active colloidal electrolytes in NMA indicates the presence of charged micelles as in aqueous and formamide solutions, and their absence in DMF and DMA as in alcoholic solutions.

A recent study¹ of electrical conductance of solutions of salts, containing an ion having a large alkyl chain viz., sodium oleate, sodium stearate, sodium palmitate, sodium deoxycholate and cetyl-trimethyl-ammonium bromide, in formamide. in this laboratory, indicates the presence of charged micelles. In order to obtain a better and general understanding of mechanism of micelle formation in solvents like formamide, it appears desirable to extend the study to some other similar solvents, viz., N-methyl acetamide (NMA), which has, like formamide, a high dielectric constant and strong hydrogen bonding, and also to some dissimilar solvents like N-N'-dimethyl formamide (DMF) and N-N'-dimethyl acetamide (DMA), both of which have only a medium dielectric constant and negligible hydrogen bonding. The result described in this communication indicate the presence of micelles in NMA but their absence in DMF and DMA.

EXPERIMENTAL

The salts used were purified in the manner as described in the previous communication¹. N-methylacetamide (D.P.I., USA) was left overnight on freshly ignited quicklime and then distilled under reduced pressure. It was fractionally crystallised and resulting liquid, obtained by melting the crystals, was again vacuum distilled. The process was repeated until the electric conductance of the sample was reduced to 10^{-7} mho. DMF and DMA, after drying on freshly ignited quicklime, were purified by repeated vacuum distillation. The specific conductance of these samples was of the order of 10^{-7} mho. Rest of the experimental procedure was the same as given in the previous communication. Equivalent conductance (λ_v) were obtained, after applying solvent correction to the measured specific conductance of solutions. Due to very low solubilities of sodium oleate, sodium palmitate, and sodium stearate in DMF and DMA, these salts could not be studied in these solvents. The λ_v vs. \sqrt{C} plots were drawn and are given in Figs. 1(a), 1(b) and 2(a), 2(b) for DMF and DMA respectively. Curves for NMA have been omitted as they were very similar to those for formamide¹ to which reference may be made.

DISCUSSION

It may be easily noticed that there is clear evidence of micelle formation in NMA but not in DMF and DMA. c.m.c. values in NMA for different salts at different temperature are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

c.m.c. values (in gm. moles/lit. $\times 10^4$) in NMA at different temperatures

	35°	40°	45°	50°
Sodium oleate	0.82	0.90	1.00	1.20
Sodium Stearate	0.80	0.88	0.95	1.20
Sodium palmitate	0.90	1.00	1.20	1.50
Sod. deoxycholate	0.70	0.90	1.00	1.50
Cetyl trimethyl-ammonium bromide	—	—	0.80	1.00

As pointed out earlier, the λ_v Vs \sqrt{C} curves of these salts in DMF and DMA (Figs. 1 and 2) clearly show that no micelle formation occurs in these solvents. The curves are almost linear without any inflexion. It may be remembered that colloidal electrolytes

Fig. 1

behave in this manner in methyl and ethyl alcohols²⁻⁷, in which micelle formation does not occur. The formation of micelles in solutions of these salts in NMA, formamide and water, and its absence in alcohol, DMF and DMA, appear to suggest the following mechanism for micelle formation.

The first essential criterion for ionic micelle formation appears to be that the solvent must have a high dielectric constant so that dissociation of electrolytes is complete in dilute solutions. This factor is present in all the solvents studied here. The second criterion is that the solvent must be capable for promoting hydrogen bond formation as is indicated by the presence of micelles in formamide, NMA and in water and its absence in DMF, DMA and in alcohols. It appears that the anionic micelles are formed through $-\text{NH}_2$ or $> \text{NH}$ groups of the solvent molecules and also that the substituted $-\text{NH}_2$ group i.e., $-\text{N}-\text{R}'$, ($\text{R} = \text{alkyl group}$) does not favour micelle formation, presumably due to the shielding of the positive charge on the nitrogen atom and the absence of H-atoms. The micelles appear to be formed by inter linking of the long anions through the hydrogen bonds formed between the H-atoms in $-\text{NH}_2$ or $> \text{NH}$ group and the anions.

Since a large number of such units are brought together with long alkyl chains in close proximity, the size of units being dependent on temperature and the force of attraction, it appears that the attractive forces would develop between long alkyl chains of neighbouring anions, as in the solid state. In DMF and DMA, both the hydrogen atoms of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group have been completely replaced by bulky 'R' groups which would shield the positive charge from interaction with the negative charge of R.COO^- ion and the micelle formation would not occur. It may be remembered here that in methyl and ethyl alcohols, ionic micelle formation does not occur because of the low dielectric constant and weak hydrogen bonding. In such solvents association occurs between the oppositely charged ions as the

Fig. 2

concentration is increased. The formation of cationic micelles in cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide, is not easy to explain by the picture of micelle formation described here. Assuming that this could occur through the negatively charged oxygen atom of the $> \text{C} = \text{O}^-$

group, micelle formation should occur in N, N¹ dialkyl substituted amides like DMF and DMA, also, which is against experimental observations. It appears that the ionic micelle formation occurs only through the hydrogen bonding although it is not easy to see how the cationic micelles could be formed in this manner. Future investigations should provide a key to this problem.

A comparison of c.m.c. values as given in Table 2 in different solvents also emphasizes the role of hydrogen bonding in micelle formation.

TABLE 2

c.m.c. values (gm. moles/lit. $\times 10^4$) in water, formamide and in NMA.

	Water	Formamide (at 35°)	NMA (at 35°)
Sodium oleate	10.00 ⁸ (25°)	5.1	0.82
Sodium stearate	—	5.2	0.80
Sodium palmitate	—	6.0	0.90
Sodium deoxychlorate	—	4.0	0.70
Cetyl-trimethyl-ammonium bromide.	7.8 ⁹ (27 \pm 2°)	5.0	0.80

It appears from Table 2 that the c.m.c. values decrease in the order water, formamide, NMA, i.e., in NMA tendency for micelle formation is strongest, this appears to be due to very high dielectric constant and strong hydrogen bonding in NMA

Thus the conductance measurements seem to indicate that ionic micelle formation is encouraged in solvents of high dielectric constant and strong hydrogen bonding. It would be desirable to substantiate these findings from studies on other physical properties of solutions of the salts containing large ions in these solvents.

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REFERENCES

1. R. Gopal and J. R. Singh, *Kolloid-Zeitschrift and Zeitschrift for polymer* 1970, 239, 699.
2. C. Evers and Kraus, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3049.
3. M. E. Laing, *Trans. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1918, 113, 435.
4. O. R. Howell and M. G. B. Robinson, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1936, 115A, 386.
5. A. F. H. Ward, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1940, 176A, 512, and *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, I, 522.
6. P. F. Grieger and C. A. Kraus, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 70, 97.
7. H. M. Bunbury and H. E. Martin, *Trans. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1914, 105, 417.
8. W. D. Harkins, *The physical Chemistry of surface Films*, p. 304 (London), 1952.
9. W. U. Malik and A. K. Jain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 631.